

Soil regeneration and horticulture production with ramial chipped woods (RCW): guidelines for successful yields and environmental sustainability

Healthy Soil for Urban Agriculture through Nutrient and Carbon Circularity (NUTRISOIL)

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Preface

The objective of this document is to provide guidance for the application of soil regeneration of peri-urban agricultural fields using carbon-rich residues from pruning waste, also known as ramial chipped wood (RCW). This guide can be useful for farmers, municipalities and stakeholders interested in soil regenerative practices soil with biomass residues. These guidelines are based on the experience and results of three crop cycles realized throughout the Proof-of Concept project “Healthy Soil for Urban Agriculture through Nutrient and Carbon Circularity” (NUTRISOIL) funded by the European Research Council (Horizon Europe, Ref: 101138151, urbag.eu/nutrisoil/).

Fig. I. Agricultural field in El Prat de Llobregat where the experiments of soil regeneration with ramial chipped wood (RCW) took place.

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1. Introduction

Urban and peri-urban agricultural lands have received little or no exogenous organic matter (OM) during the past decades mainly because of the substitution of organic residues by mineral fertilizers (Garcia-Pausas et al., 2017). Exogenous OM is defined as any plant or animal residue applied and provides carbon and nutrients for the soil microbiota, including plants, fungi, insects and other microorganisms. The application of exogenous OM contributes to soil organic matter (SOM) pools which improves soil structure, porosity, water infiltration and retention and acts as a carbon sequestrator, reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Bot and Benites, 2005). Under healthy conditions, plants and microorganisms share a symbiotic relationship in which the roots provide the carbon exudates necessary to feed microorganisms that will then mineralize the nutrients retained in SOM for plant uptake (Jacoby et al., 2017; Ma et al., 2022). Any disturbance associated to farming, such as tillage, ploughing or vegetation burning, accelerates OM disappearance and leads to land degradation (Bot and Benites, 2005).

In impoverished soils, high temperatures, which are exacerbated by climate change, increase the mineralization of SOM, further reducing organic carbon and nutrient pools necessary to improve soil biochemical processes and extend crop rooting patterns (Wander et al., 2007, 1994). Additionally, because most horticultural crops do not leave large amounts of plant residues and because of intensive tillage, organic carbon levels in horticultural soils are typically low. In low SOM conditions, due to soil compaction, roots colonize poorly in the soil. This results in poor cycling and assimilation of nutrients for crop growth (Celestina et al., 2019), which is compensated by intensifying the use of mineral fertilizers and further deterioration of the soil. Thus, regenerating soils in urban and peri-urban areas by replenishing organic carbon is key in optimizing and reducing fertilizers.

To remediate this situation, reducing or avoiding tilling in addition to increasing the content of soil organic carbon (SOC) can promote biological activity, facilitate nitrogen distribution and retention, and increase resilience to extreme climate events (Haddaway et al., 2017; Krauss et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2025). While the use of compost can contribute to increase SOM over the medium term, the use of ramial chipped wood (RCW) can solve the problem in the very short term (few months), due to its high decomposability and the possibility of applying high doses (Jaime-Rodríguez et al.,

2025). Various studies have demonstrated the positive impacts of adding woody residues in improving soil health, plant growth, nutrients availability and uptake, and water retention (Fontana et al., 2023; Jaime-Rodríguez et al., 2025; Li et al., 2020; Menzies Pluer et al., 2020; Richardson et al., 2023). Some work is already under way to restore soil health and regeneration with similar approaches at the European (LivingSoiLL Project, Soil Capital Farming, SUS-SOIL Project). A more local example is the Regensol project (funded by the Generalitat de Catalunya and European Union Agricultural Funds for Rural Development (2022-2024); [Regensol](#)), which consisted in the application of RCW biomass followed by sweet potato cultivation in 12 commercial fields in Catalonia (Spain), with the goal to produce competitive yields compared to conventional practices, increase the OM in the soil to reduce the need of synthetic fertilizers, improve the quality of the crops, and decrease mineral fertilizers consumption. Results showed that RCW application for sweet potato cultivation led to comparable yields to conventional fertilizations and increased levels of SOC and nitrogen.

The project NUTRISOIL aims to add to this growing community of scientists and farmers by analysing crop with RCW not only in terms of yield, but also in terms of soil regeneration and reduction of environmental impacts. Various crop cycles have been carried out under various fertilization and RCW treatments, for which we have analysed SOM, nutrient budgets, and gaseous emissions of CO₂, CH₄, NH₃ and N₂O - more concretely, two spinach cycles and one sweet potato cycle in a 12-month study on a commercial peri-urban field in El Prat de Llobregat (Barcelona). Chapters 2 and 3 are dedicated to describing these experiments and analytical methodology. Based on these experiments and the results of the environmental and agronomical analysis, we have compiled a set of guidelines for farmers (chapter 4), municipalities and stakeholders (chapter 5). Chapter 6 presents the final considerations of the project, highlighting key findings and practical recommendations for the effective use of RCW in soil regeneration, climate mitigation, and sustainable farm management.

2. Methodology

Fig.1. Location of the field within the metropolitan area of Barcelona where the NUTRISOIL experiments took place. Green areas correspond to agricultural land.

2.1. Experimental design

The experiment was set in a peri-urban field in El Prat de Llobregat (Barcelona, Spain) (Figure 2) from February 2024 until January 2025 and consisted of three crop cycles in two different areas of the field, both of 132 m². The area is characterized by a Mediterranean climate according to Köppen-Geiger classification (Kottek et al., 2006). The main characteristics of the soil before the experiments are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the soil where the experiment took place.

<u>Main characteristics</u>						
Type of soil	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Lime (%)	pH	Organic matter (%)	C/N
Loam	24	48	28	7.75	1.84	8.32

<u>Macronutrient</u>						
Total N (mg/kg)	P available (mg/kg)	CaCO ₃ active (%)	Ca (meq/100 g)	Mg (meq/100 g)	K (meq/100 g)	Na (meq/100 g)
1.282	52.1	5.95	14.9	2.4	1.14	1.68

<u>Microelements</u>			
Fe (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)	Cu (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)
18	5.11	32.2	18.5

Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea L.*) was cultivated from February to April 2024 and then again from October to January 2025; the field was covered with polyethylene films between the

two cycles to avoid weed growth, soil erosion and nutrient losses. In the second field, sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* cv. *Beauregard*) was cultivated from May to September 2024. Each experiment consisted of four treatments carried out in sixteen plots of 7.5 m x 1.1 m (arranged in four lanes separated by one meter), with four replicants for each treatment (Figure 2). Treatments were the following:

- NPK: mineral fertilizer with 20% of nitrogen, 7% of phosphorous and 10% of potassium.
- SON: struvite ($MgNH_4PO_4$) and organic nitrogen. Struvite is slow-release fertilizer recovered in wastewater treatment plants; it contains 5.7% of N, 12.5% of P, and 9.9% of Mg, making it a valuable nutrient source for plants. The rest of the nitrogen was applied with Labinor N-10 (LABINOR N10), an organic fertilizer, by-product of the meat industry, containing 10% of N.
- COM: compost from Torrelles de Llobregat composting plant.
- RCWON: ramial chipped wood from plane trees residues of the metropolitan area of Barcelona and organic nitrogen (LABINOR N10).
- RCW: ramial chipped wood from plane trees residues of the metropolitan area of Barcelona.

The amount of fertilizers applied is show in Table 2 while nutrient contents of different fertilizers and RCW are shown in the appendix (Appendix 1, Table S1, S3 and S4)

Table 2. Amount of fertilizers applied for each treatment.

	NPK	Struvite	Organic nitrogen	Compost	Ramial chipped wood
Spinach (first cycle)	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha
NPK	0.37				
SON		0.14	0.66		
COM				13	
RCWON			1.2		151.5
Spinach (second cycle)	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha
NPK	0.37				
SON		0.14	0.66		
COM					
RCWON					
Sweet potato	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha	t/ha
SON		0.46	1.71		
COM				10.78	
RCWON			2.96		151.5
RCW					151.5

Fig. 2. Distribution of plots (7.5 x 1.1 meters) and allocation of treatments in the experimental field for the sweet potato and the two spinach cycles. NPK: plots fertilized with mineral fertilizers; SON: plots fertilized with struvite and organic nitrogen; COM: plots fertilized with compost; RCW: plots were ramial chipped wood was incorporated; RCWON: plots were ramial chipped woods was incorporated and extra organic nitrogen was added.

Biomass of RCW from plane trees (*Platanus occidentalis L.*) was collected from urban parks and road trees of the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona. After pruning, the biomass residues were trimmed to a size of 5 cm of length before the incorporation into the soil, as shown in figure 3.

Fig. 3. A) Pile of RCW before the incorporation; B) details of the RCW.

To determine the amount of fertilizer, RCW, or recovered nutrients required for each treatment, an initial quantification of the nutrients already present in the soil and irrigation water was carried out. Samples of soil and water were collected before planting to understand nutrient contents, physical and chemical characteristics (Table 1; Appendix 1, Table S2). Then, based on nutrient required by each crop (Table 3), a simple mass balance was performed to determine the amount that each treatment needed to be applied to the soil.

Table 3. Nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium needs of spinach and sweet potato.

	N (kg ha ⁻¹)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg ha ⁻¹)	K ₂ O (kg ha ⁻¹)
Spinach	72	28.8	140.8
Sweet potato	213.9	69.6	79.6

Additional nitrogen was applied to RCWON plots (during the first spinach cycle and the sweet potato cycle) beside of what was present in the pruning residues (Appendix A, table S1). This was done because the high immobilization rate of microorganisms could have influenced plant performance.

2.2. Pruning residues and fertilizer incorporation

The soil was prepared by tilling to a depth of 20 cm using a rotary tiller. Pruning residues were incorporated with a rotary tiller 10 days before other fertilizers and approximately

two weeks before planting. Granular fertilizers (mineral, struvite and organic nitrogen) and compost were spread on the field with broadcast application (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Incorporation of fertilizers: A) fertilization with NPK; B) fertilization with compost; C) incorporation of RCW residues with rotary tiller; D) application of organic nitrogen after pruning incorporation.

2.3. Irrigation management

Plants were irrigated with well water using drip irrigation for all crop cycles and the amount of water was decided based on the needs of the plants, according to the guidelines by Baixauli and Maroto Borrego (2016). In the same area, furrow irrigation is very popular for most crops due to the easy implementation and the habit of washing the salts that might accumulate on the field. In our experiments, drip irrigation was adopted to minimize water consumption, avoid nutrient addition and possible disruptions from the municipality during droughts episodes.

During the spinach cycles, every lane of the field had three irrigation tubes with a dripper every 20 cm, while, for sweet potato cultivation, one irrigation tube was installed (Figure

5).

Fig. 5. Polyethylene tubes for drip irrigation during A) spinach and B) sweet potato cultivation.

2.4. Gas analysis with static chambers

The CO_2 , CH_4 , NH_3 and N_2O were measured with a static chamber set-up, as shown in figure 6. The chambers were made of polypropylene and painted in white to minimize indoor heating.

Fig. 6. A) Base of the chamber with spinach plants; B) measurements of CO_2 , CH_4 and NH_3 with portable gas analysers; C) measurements of N_2O with syringe and flasks for samples storage; D) scheme of gas measurements.

3. Field results

3.1. Yield of spinach and sweet potato

The results of our experiments show a big difference between the yield of the two spinach cycles with the one of sweet potato (Table 4). In both cycles of spinach, the use of pruning residues did not produce similar yield to other treatments (NPK, SON, COM). The growth of plants fertilized with pruning residues was slower and the leaves appeared pale, compared to other treatments (Figure 7).

Table 4. Yield results of different treatments between the three crop cycles expressed in kilos per square meter.

Crop	NPK (kg m ⁻²)	SON (kg m ⁻²)	COM (kg m ⁻²)	RCWON (kg m ⁻²)	RCW (kg m ⁻²)
Spinach (Feb. - Apr.)	2.84	2.45	2.44	1.16	
Spinach (Oct. - Jan.)	1.63	1.12	0.84	0.32	
Sweet potato (May - Sept.)		1.55	1.56	1.72	1.99

Fig. 7. State of the plots on the 49th day after planting (Feb. – Apr. cycle).

A: NPK; B) SON; C) COM; D) RCWON.

On the other hand, the incorporation of pruning for sweet potato cultivation (with or without additional nitrogen), produced higher yields compared to the other treatments (SON, COM). Our findings agree with previous research that investigated on the positive impact of carbon rich residues on sweet potato cultivation (Jaime-Rodríguez et al., 2025; Richardson et al., 2023). Previous studies have shown that high doses of mineral nitrogen have negative effects on the production of sweet potato storage roots (Conz et al., 2021; Darko et al., 2020), favouring vegetative and possible weed growth (Duan et al., 2018). These findings agree with our data, showing that high doses of available nitrogen (e.g. NO₃⁻ or NH₄⁺) added with struvite or compost produced less kilos compared to plots

treated with RCW. Additionally, we noticed that RCW incorporation decreased vegetative and weed growth compared to the other treatments (Figure 8).

Fig. 8. Vegetative portions of sweet potato plants. A) Plants of SON treatment; B) plants of COM treatment; C) plants of RCWON treatment; D) plants of RCW treatment.

3.2. Emissions from the crops

Daily averaged emissions estimated from the observations are shown in table 4 while cumulative emissions can be consulted in the appendix 2 (Table S6).

Table 4. Table with daily emissions of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and NH₃ of the three crop cycles.

		CO₂ Daily emissions	CH₄ Daily emissions	N₂O Daily emissions	NH₃ Daily emissions
Spinach (first cycle)	Days	(kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)
NPK	49	83.2	-1.5	7.4	0.13
SON	49	91.5	-1.2	7.9	0.14
COM	49	79.4	-1.8	0.9	0.15
RCWON	66	370.9	-1.2	1.1	0.13
Spinach (second cycle)	Days	(kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)
NPK	92	103.7	-1.2	4.7	6.71
SON	92	107.5	-1	3.2	-3.37
COM	92	78.8	-0.7	3.7	-0.47
RCWON	92	145.2	-0.8	2.3	-0.65
Sweet potato	Days	(kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹ day⁻¹)
SON	122	194.2	2	7.6	7.26
COM	122	211.9	-5.1	0.6	11.24
RCWON	122	708.2	0.7	1	1.29
RCW	122	672.1	-35.3	0.3	9.32

Carbon additions with RCW will lead to high emissions of CO₂ at the beginning, mainly due to the degradation of hemicellulose and cellulose compounds. However, except for initial high CO₂ values, emissions will decrease through time, reaching levels similar to other treatments (Figure 9). Comparing the results of the two cycles of spinach, we can notice a reduction in daily CO₂ of 60.9%, showing that a big portion of organic carbon was degraded or incorporated as organic matter during the previous months.

Sweet potato cycle (May - Sept. 2024)

Fig. 9. CO₂ emissions during the sweet potato cycle. 60 days after RCW incorporation, CO₂ daily emissions started to decrease drastically, reaching similar values to the other treatments (struvite with organic nitrogen and compost) at the end of the experiment.

3.3. Soil organic carbon (SOC) and nitrogen increases in the short-term

After one cycle of sweet potato during the Regensol project, SOC increased by an average of 0.45%. This increase specifically pertains the carbon found in fine earth soil particles (< 2 mm). Larger RCW debris will continue to decompose over the coming months, further contributing to SOC accumulation in the soil. Similarly, after RCW application and sweet potato harvest, 700 kg ha⁻¹ of nitrogen were found incorporated to the fine earth and is expected to remain stable in soil. Indeed, reduced N₂O emissions were found in treatments including RCW (Table 4). We might expect similar results also for our experiments conducted during the NUTRISOIL project, since the amount of RCW applied was the similar.

4. Guidelines for farmers

4.1. Assessing the state of soil

Farmers are advised to first determine the status of their soil by observing rooting patterns as an indicator of soil compaction. Guides to visually evaluate soil structure can be consulted to assess the state of soil, root penetration, water availability and soil aeration (Ball et al., 2007). The guide provided by Ball et al. (2007) is fast and simple, based on a

visual evaluation of the state of soil in 5–15 minutes and it assess a score from 1 (good structure) to 5 (poor structure). The first step is to remove a block of soil of 15 cm thick using a spade and placing the sample onto a sheet or tray (preferably light-coloured). Then, using hands, the block is divided into smaller pieces of 1.5–2 cm which are visually assessed by shape (rounded, cubical, sharp), porosity (presence of cracks, micro and macropores), roots presence (growth through the aggregates or only around?) and ease of break up to assign a score. A summarized version of the guide is available here ([Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure](#)) while a video of the sampling process is available here ([VESS Demonstration Film](#)).

Here we can observe different stages of soil degradation according to the guide:

Structure quality	Size and appearance of aggregates	Visible porosity and Roots	Appearance after break-up: various soils	Appearance after break-up: same soil different tillage	Distinguishing feature	Appearance and description of natural or reduced fragment of ~ 1.5 cm diameter
Sq1 Friable Aggregates readily crumble with fingers	Mostly < 6 mm after crumbling	Highly porous Roots throughout the soil	 The action of breaking the block is enough to reveal them. Large aggregates are composed of smaller ones, held by roots.			
Sq2 Intact Aggregates easy to break with one hand	A mixture of porous, rounded aggregates from 2mm - 7 cm. No clods present	Most aggregates are porous Roots throughout the soil	 Aggregates when obtained are rounded, very fragile, crumble very easily and are highly porous.			
Sq3 Firm Most aggregates break with one hand	A mixture of porous aggregates from 2mm -10 cm; less than 30% are <1 cm. Some angular, non-porous aggregates (clods) may be present	Macropores and cracks present. Porosity and roots both within aggregates.	 Aggregate fragments are fairly easy to obtain. They have few visible pores and are rounded. Roots usually grow through the aggregates.			
Sq4 Compact Requires considerable effort to break aggregates with one hand	Mostly large > 10 cm and sub-angular non-porous; horizontal/platy also possible; less than 30% are <7 cm	Few macropores and cracks All roots are clustered in macropores and around aggregates	 Aggregate fragments are easy to obtain when soil is wet, in cube shapes which are very sharp-edged and show cracks internally.			
Sq5 Very compact Difficult to break up	Mostly large > 10 cm, very few < 7 cm, angular and non-porous	Very low porosity. Macropores may be present. May contain anaerobic zones. Few roots, if any, and restricted to cracks	 Aggregate fragments are easy to obtain when soil is wet, although considerable force may be needed. No pores or cracks are visible usually.			

Fig. 9. Visual evaluation of soil structure (Source: [VESS](#), Ball et al., (2007)).

This guide is not as precise as soil test but is an easy and fast way to understand the state of soil and its level of degradation. A soil test is useful to know the amount of nutrients present in your field, what lacks, and whether the soil conditions are right for your crops. It generally tells you the texture of your soil (percentage of sand, clay and lime), pH, electrical conductivity, content of SOC, C/N ration and content of macro and micronutrients. With these information, farmers can determine which crops and practices are best suited to their soil conditions, decide if or when to apply fertilizers, and prevent environmental damage caused by overfertilization. Specifically, knowing the content of

SOC and C/N is important to understand whether your field is degraded and at what rate. In temperate regions, a SOC concentration of 2% is generally considered the critical threshold below which a serious decline in soil quality and yield may occur (Loveland and Webb, 2003; Lorenz et al., 2019).

The results of our analysis, performed by an external laboratory, can be consulted in the appendix (Figure S1), with prices usually ranging between 60 and 90€ (for Spain).

4.2. The slake test

Another easy and cheap way of assessing the state of your soil is performing a slake test. It demonstrates the stability of soil when exposed to rapid wetting: the longer soil takes to break down in water, the more stable it is. Stable soil with high contents of OM resists erosion from wind and water and improves water infiltration and holding properties.

Additional information can be consulted on practical guides ([FAO](#); [NRCS](#)) and video demonstrations ([USDA NRCS Slake test](#); [Iowa NRCS](#);) by research centres and farmers.

To perform the test, you will need:

- A clear glass or plastic container (e.g. jar or beaker) filled with water.
- A mesh support that will fit into the top half of the container.
- Soil aggregates collected from your field (preferably dry).
- A stopwatch to record the time needed to the soil sample to disaggregate in water.

Procedure

1. Place the wired mesh into the jar filled with water.
2. Place the soil aggregate sample onto the mesh so that the whole sample is submerged.
3. Use the stopwatch to time how quickly the sample breaks down. This is especially useful when comparing the sample before and after soil regeneration following RCW incorporation.

Taking pictures and comparing the two soil samples (before and after RCW incorporation) is useful to visually estimate the improvements in soil structure due to an increase in OM (Figure 10).

Knowing the state of your soil, through both a visual and a lab test, is essential to assess the changes that occur after RCW incorporation. We hereby suggest you to perform two (or more) tests: one before RCW application and one some months after.

Fig. 10. Comparison of different soil samples after slaking test. The sample on the left shows good aggregation and does not break apart in water, showing better health conditions than the other sample.

4.3. Quantity and type of RCW to apply

The primary goal of RCW application is to feed the soil microbiota and stimulate its ecological functions. It is particularly recommended for soils low in organic matter, where it helps improve physical soil conditions and enhance microbial metabolism. This, in turn, may improve plant access to nutrients retained in the soil and contribute to a more natural nutrient availability. While this natural fertility tends to be moderate—especially when compared to conventionally fertilised soils—it is expected to support improved crop nutritional quality, including an increase in bioactive compounds (Jaime-Rodríguez et al., 2025). Besides providing carbon, pruning residues also supply macro and micronutrients in high doses (Table S4). However, it is important to note that the addition of woody materials can sometimes lead to a temporary reduction in macro and micronutrient availability due to increased microbial activity. It is therefore advisable to apply RCW in combination with crops that can cope with temporary nutrient shortages, which often occur in the first months following incorporation.

Rather than looking at specific species, we suggest the farmers to select the pruning source according to the carbon – nitrogen ratio (C/N), that should range between 40 and 70. Palm

trees is not recommended since its wood is too tough and difficult to chip, sometimes causing damage to the machines. The optimal size for RCW should be less than 5 cm in length and 3 cm in diameter, to avoid problems during the incorporation. However, the size of the material resulting from the trimming processes of pruning biomass will greatly depend on the available machinery, so farmers might need to adapt to the available size. According to Regensol guidelines, the recommended application rate for initiating regeneration ranges from 10 to 15 kg m⁻² (100–150 ton ha⁻¹) and do not depend on soil texture (% of sand, silt and clay), physical and chemical properties, but rather on the existing OM content of the soil. In our experiments, we applied 15 kg m⁻² prior to planting spinach and sweet potato.

4.4. How to apply the RCW

Similarly to compost fertilization, farmers can distribute RCW by using a compost or manure spreader attached to their tractor (Figure 11 and 12) and successively incorporate it in the soil using a rotary tiller (Figure 13). For small portions of land, RCW can be distributed on the field with wheelbarrows and incorporated with a walking tractor (Figure 13, right).

Fig. 11. Farmer using a spreader trailer to distribute compost on his field. A similar approach could be adopted to spread RCW. Source: [Stop Waste](#).

Fig. 12. Manure spreader used to spread RCW. Source: [Cal Notari](#).

Fig. 13. Ramial chipped wood (RCW) incorporation using tractor rotary tiller (left) and walking tractor for small portions of land (right). A video of RCW incorporation can be consulted here: [Regensol+](#).

Since only short-term results up to a couple of years are available to date, we are still not sure about how often RCW needs to be reapplied. We suggest to regularly perform soil analysis to assess the content of organic carbon and/or visually analyse the state of soil (Ball et al., 2007) and try to maintain high values of OM ($> 2.5 - 3\%$). Additionally, adopting sustainable farming practices such as little or no-till, crop rotations, cover cropping and fertilization with compost will help preserve high OM contents. Our hypothesis, based on Regensol results so far, is that with this kind of field management, additional doses of RCW are not needed since SOC is not disrupted or depleted.

4.5. Crop selection: sweet potato and possible alternatives.

Based on results of the NUTRISOIL and Regensol projects, RCW application seems to do best for nitrogen-fixing crops such as sweet potato. The enhanced metabolisms and pool of microorganisms caused by RCW incorporation might cause excessive competition for the nitrogen. For this reason, we recommend planting sweet potato or other N-fixing plants (e.g. fava bean) as started crops (right after pruning incorporation) to avoid the risk of nitrogen deficiency (Figure 14). According to the results of the Regensol and NUTRISOIL project, the “Beauregard” and “O’ Henry” varieties are the ones that performed better with RCW application (Figure 15). The optimal temperature for plant growth is 25 to 28 °C during the day and 17 to 20 °C at night, while temperatures < 15°C limit growth and temperatures < 8°C are too cold for any production. In colder climates, fava beans could be grown as starter crop, due to its tolerance to low temperatures (up to -15 °C) and optimal growth ranging from 18 to 27 °C (Jensen et al., 2010). High temperatures are also favourable for the proliferation of soil microbiota and in accelerating their metabolism, therefore it is preferred to incorporate RCW during Spring-Summer months.

Fig. 14. Sweet potato vines before (A) and after planting (B); sweet potato plants two months after planting (C) and tubers harvest (D). Source: [Regensol](#).

Fig. 15. Most suited varieties of sweet potato after RCW incorporation. Source: [Tatorman](#).

What could be grown after pruning incorporation and sweet potato harvest? Farmers that participated in the Regensol project achieved the best results by growing legumes, onions, carrots, cruciferous or a combination between spinach and fava beans as subsequent crops.

It is not recommended to plant leafy greens, such as spinach, right after RCW incorporation, as their high demand for mineral nitrogen may not be met due to increased microbial activity that temporarily immobilizes nitrogen. During our cycles of spinach, we noticed that the plants in plots with RCW were growing slower compared to other treatments and many leaves appeared yellow, symptoms of nitrogen deficiency.

4.6. Alternatives to RCW: compost, bokashi and cover crops.

There are alternatives to RCW that also increase the unstable carbon content of the soil and help regenerate it:

- **Bokashi:** fermented organic matter that can be prepared with a mix of plant residues, rock granulate and microorganisms in anaerobic conditions (Boechat et al., 2013). The flexibility of the recipe and its low-cost makes bokashi the ideal product for many situation. In Rotterdam, the municipality collaborated with its citizens to collect the leaves on roads and sidewalk to produce bokashi (Figure 16). Its implementation showed positive results, including increased productivity of ornamental plants, enhanced soil biodiversity, and an average annual accumulation of 3 cm of humus (Gemeente Rotterdam).

Fig. 16. Bokashi made with leaves (up); effect of Bokashi fertilization on ornamental plants in Vroesenpark, Rotterdam (down). Source: [Rotterdam Circulair](#)

- **Compost:** a good alternative to RCW to increase the OM, feeding the microbiota and adding nutrients to the soil (Figure 17). Some popular alternatives are vermicompost and insect frass, both produced with crop residues or organic waste (Ducasse et al., 2022; Poveda, 2021). In Barcelona, municipal compost is used for parks and gardens or by farmers. However, special attention should be taken on the limits of its application, that follow regional, national or European laws based on contents of nitrogen, heavy metals, plastic and other pollutants, and to its high P content relative to N. Another limitation lays in the stable nature of compost: the use labile organic sources may decrease SOC stocks, since it may rapidly decompose and stimulate the decomposition of additional SOC (Angers et al., 2010). Oppositely, the use of recalcitrant sources of OM like RCW may favour SOC stocks (Bhogal et al., 2009; Molina-Herrera and Romanyà, 2015).

Fig. 17. Compost fertilization before spinach planting during the NUTRISOIL project (left); homemade vermicompost (right).

- Cover crops:** cover crops can be grown with the main crop, between crop cycles, or in nearby field, leaving their carbon and nitrogen-rich residues on the soil acting as green manures (Figure 18) (Scavo and Mauromicale, 2020). Cover crops have many benefits such as increasing SOM, carbon sequestration, improving bulk density and soil porosity, weed control, reduction of nutrient leaching and improvement of nutrient availability. (Scavo et al., 2022). Legumes cover crops can fix atmospheric nitrogen thanks to their symbiosis with *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bacteria and, as shown by Möller et al. (2008), can add between 60 and 80 kg of nitrogen per hectare of soil. Other cover crops, such as sorghum, can also promote atmospheric N fixation by diazotrophic bacteria occurring in the rhizosphere (Barros et al., 2020; Hara et al., 2019). This practice could be very helpful to increase the fertility, especially in empty portions of land that are not cultivated during the current season. Similarly to compost, cover crops have positive effects only in the short term and its effects in increasing the OM and nutrient contents are not present in the long term if soil is disturbed.

Fig. 18. A) Rocket crushing using a tractor equipped with roller crimper B) dry cover crops applied as mulch for tomato cultivation; C) cash crops and cover crops (in the inter row) cultivation.

4.7. How to reduce emissions

During our experiment, we measured emissions of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and NH₃ to understand the environmental impact of different fertilization strategies. CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O are greenhouse gases and primary contributors to global warming, while NH₃ is a pollutant which contaminates the local air. It is important to know that CH₄ and N₂O have 28 and 265 higher global warming potential than CO₂ (IPCC, 2014). NH₃ can lead to the formation of secondary particulate compounds in the atmosphere related to human health problems (Misselbrook et al., 2014; Wyer et al., 2022) and generate indirect N₂O emissions (Erisman et al., 2007; Alfaro et al., 2018).

Whereas CO₂ emissions are mainly associated to soil respiration and field management (Sainju et al., 2006), CH₄ is correlated to manure application and lasting anoxia conditions (Cole et al., 1997). Emissions of N₂O in soils are controlled by nitrification and denitrification processes and are influenced by nitrogen source, temperature, soil density and water-filled pore space (Signor and Cerri, 2013; Islam et al., 2020). NH₃ volatilization is related to urea (CH₄N₂O), ammonium (NH₄⁺) and manure application (Bouwman et al., 2002; Velthof et al., 2012).

Here are some guidelines to reduce or keep emissions low to reduce the environmental impact of crop production:

- **Reduce fertilizer inputs:** for the second cycle of spinach, we can notice that mineral fertilizers and struvite with organic nitrogen produced higher emissions

of CO₂ compared to plants with compost (where no inputs were added for this cycle). This increase in CO₂ was caused by fertilization inputs, which partially fed the microbiota, leading to enhanced respiration. Similar results were recorded by Toonsiri et al. (2016) in lettuce cultivation, where CO₂ emissions increased in plots that received fertilization compared to those with zero inputs.

- **Choose organic N sources:** our results evidence that, even if nitrogen doses were higher in plots where compost or RCW were applied, the adoption of organic N will lead to lower N₂O emissions compared to the mineral alternatives (Table 5). For the first spinach cycle, for example, 0.31% of the nitrogen applied was emitted as N₂O in NPK plots, while in RCW plots, this value was only 0.002%, even though nitrogen inputs in RCW were 31.7 times higher.

Table 5. Emission factors of different nitrogen sources, with RCW and RCWON obtaining the lowest values in all cycles.

Percentage of emitted nitrogen as N₂O

	Spinach (first cycle)	Spinach (second cycle)	Sweet potato
Mineral fertilizer	0.31%	0.38%	
Struvite + organic nitrogen	0.34%	0.26%	0.30%
Compost	0.01%	0.06%	0.02%
RCWON	0.002%	0.006%	0.005%
RCW			0.002%

- **Adopt drip irrigation:** by choosing drip irrigation rather than furrow one, the risk of flooding the field is strongly reduced. Flooding irrigation is associated to nutrient losses through percolation and increased N₂O and CH₄ emissions, due to the formation of anaerobic conditions in the soil. Farmers can easily install polyethylene tubes for drip irrigation, as shown in figures 5 and 8.
- **Carbon retention after RCW incorporation:** only 16% of the total carbon incorporated with the RCW was emitted as CO₂ over the course of both spinach cycles. It is important to note that there was a gap between the two cycles—the first ending in late April and the second beginning on October 12th—during which CO₂ emissions likely increased due to warmer temperatures and ongoing microbial activity. However, the sweet potato cycle, which spanned this intermediate period (from early May to late September), showed that 36% of the

incorporated carbon was emitted as CO₂. Taken together, these findings suggest that, from February to January, approximately 52% (16% + 36%) of the added carbon was emitted as CO₂, while the remaining portion was retained in the soil, either incorporated into fine earth particles or still present in larger RCW fragments undergoing further decomposition

- **Reduced NH₃ volatilization:** in order to reduce the risks of NH₃ emissions, avoid using manure, urea-based fertilizers and broadcast fertilization.

5. Guidelines for municipalities and stakeholders

The guidelines contained in this section are based on the results of three workshops conducted for the NUTRISOIL project. These workshops involved key stakeholders within agriculture, soil management, waste and wastewater management, and organisations within the urban community (e.g. agricultural producers, farmers unions, community associations, waste managers, municipality representatives, municipal parks and garden services, researchers, etc.). Two workshops were carried out at a local AMB level and one at the European level involving eight cities.

5.1. RCW collection, storage and machinery

Municipal or regional entities, responsible for maintaining green areas, generate significant volumes of pruning waste. In Barcelona, the municipality maintains approximately 310,000 trees. With tree pruning cycles every five years and shrub trimming every three months, this biomass could be redirected to enrich 2,938 hectares of the El Pratt de Llobregat agricultural park (Gestión de los espacios verdes de Barcelona; Gestión del arbolado).

We suggest storing recovered biomass under dry and cool conditions and away from rainfall, to avoid nutrient losses through emissions and leachates (Figure 20). To streamline operations, we advise municipalities to invest in decentralised processing infrastructure, such as electric shredders and mobile woodchippers (Figure 21), placed in biomass-dense areas. These machines should be designed to trim the residues to the recommended dimensions (5 cm of length and 3 cm of diameter).

Fig. 20. Wrong and correct way of storing RCW to avoid nutrient losses.

Fig. 21. Mobile woodchipper. Source: [Jas P. Wilson](#)

Additionally, GPS tracking should be implemented to improve biomass traceability. Helping waste managers detect contamination sources and to respond in a timely manner.

5.2. Education programs

We suggest municipalities to implement education campaigns that address the negative downstream impacts of fertilisers, pesticides, herbicides and litter. For example, plastic that is not separated from the biomass before being processed will result in microplastics entering food systems (Figure 22).

Fig. 22. Plastic contamination in compost. Source: [Scopetani et al., 2022](#)

We suggest placing signage around green areas to connect the use of biomass for agricultural food production. High quality biomass should be compared with poor quality biomass, and the impacts on food production should be made clear. While areas identified as contamination hotspots through tracking initiatives (e.g., door-to-door collection, GPS and smart containers) should be given a warning of their negative impact through pamphlets or a municipal letter. If contamination persists, the polluter should be fined for continuous contamination rendering the final product unusable for agricultural application.

We suggest education programs to be hands-on and interactive to enable the individual to learn through trial and error in a controlled setting. We suggest including in education programs: the identification of correct organic waste for agricultural use, opportunities to touch and smell high quality wood chips and compost with poor quality, and parks growing produce with recovered organic matter to reconnect individuals with their food production (Figure 23).

Fig 23. Community gardens connect citizens to food production. Source: [Huertocity](https://www.huertocity.com/)

5.3. RCW transportation, distribution and incentives

Municipal-private contracts should explicitly identify farmers as the final recipients of recovered biomass and compost. We suggest that logistics and distribution be managed by the municipality or by contracted third parties.

Transport solutions should be tailored to field accessibility and biomass volume. Accessibility of the land and volume of pruning biomass, different types of trucks could be used. In our case, 1 ton of RCW was applied to regenerate 66 m² of soil for sweet potato cultivation. This residue had a volume of 6.73 m³ and was transported on a single trip by a van, but small trucks or vehicles equipped with trailers could also have been used. Alternatively, farmers could use their own tractors and trailers to collect shredded RCW from nearby storage centres (Figure 24).

Fig. 24. Tractor equipped with trailer that could be used to recollect RCW at the storage facility.

Source: [Palmse Trailer](#)

To cover 1 ha of land with RCW (151 ton ha⁻¹ or 1,009 m³), we suggest implementing larger vehicles (e.g., truck with freight; figure 25). If reaching the field is problematic due to narrow roads or other issues, various trips with smaller vehicles are preferred. Where feasible, trucks equipped with mechanical arms are ideal for loading biomass onto the spreader machine or trailer.

Fig. 25. Unloading of RCW directly on the field. Source: [Cal Notari](#).

To aid farmers in the adoption of these techniques, municipalities can offer shared or rented spreading equipment (ideally electric-powered) and deliver RCW to farms or easy-access pick-up points. We suggest providing technical assistance and labour support, especially for small-scale producers.

Farmers using RCW or municipal recovered organic material should be compensated for doing so, or incentive campaigns encouraging the sales of their produce should be implemented. This could be marketing campaigns to support farmers, subsidising the produce or green procurement policies.

5.4. Institutional coherence and policy integration

Effective circular bioeconomy implementation requires cross-sector governance. Cities should coordinate amongst diverse stakeholders to develop strategic circularity. An interdisciplinary committee was viewed favourably by stakeholder workshop participants as this would identify co-benefits, align strategies and promote participatory policymaking.

Currently, waste classification is complex, with 15 different waste classifications requiring different treatment methods. We suggest simplifying this to facilitate the recovery of organic materials. Moreover, each alternative fertiliser has its own regulatory requirements for treatment, nutrient content, and application ([Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación](#)), creating barriers for farmers looking to phase out mineral fertilisers.

Policy coherence across EU, national, and local levels is necessary. Spanish Law 7/2022 mandates compliance with [EU Regulations 2019/1009](#), which prohibits sludge in compost for CE-marked products. This restricts domestic sales of sludge-based compost, yet imports from other EU countries remain legal. Thus, regulatory harmonization must reflect local realities, with a focus on soil nutrient control and improved access to high-quality recovered organic material for farmers. Other inconsistencies—like stricter rules for recovered nutrients than synthetic fertilizers—discourage adoption, including, 1) the Nitrates Directive 91/676/EEC [Council of the European Communities](#) (Council Directive, 2008), establishing land application limitation of fertilizers derived from organic residues in nitrate-vulnerable zones ($170 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), yet no equivalent limitation exist for synthetic fertilizers, and 2) the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC [European Parliament](#) (Directive 2008/98/EC), lacking a EU-wide “end-of-waste” criteria, keeping organic fertilizers such as compost and struvite under a “waste” classification unless

certified under more regulations, resulting in more paperwork and costs than synthetic fertilizers for transportation and storage. Regulatory clarity and long-term stability are critical to support public and private investment.

Sustainability accounting should evolve to include environmental and social costs of soil degradation and food production. We hereby suggest that regenerative practices be recognized and rewarded through ecosystem service payments and social economy mechanisms.

6. Final considerations and conclusions

With the results showed in the previous sections we can draw some conclusions.

- The use of RCW is recommended on soils poor in organic matter. It is essential to combine the incorporation of RCW with crops such as sweet potato or other N-fixing crops, to overcome the N deficiency during the first few months. We have evidence that after sweet potato, soil nutrient availability is good for most crops without further fertilization.
- To maintain elevated levels of SOC in the long term, reduced or no-till practices are preferred. These practices, when combined with green manuring or compost application, will keep the SOC high, increase nutrient and water availability and promote soil biodiversity.
- Farmers need support and collaboration from the municipality or other organizations to shred, transport and incorporate the pruning residues. In this way, they do not need to purchase additional machinery or spend too much time for this practice.
- Farmers should be encouraged to use RCW by receiving subsidies and/or reduced taxations, due to their help with municipal waste disposal and positive effects on the ecosystem.
- Although CO₂ emissions were higher in plots where pruning residues were incorporated, this process contributed to long-term soil carbon sequestration with consequent effects on soil health, water and nutrient retention. From a broader perspective, this practice can also offset CO₂, N₂O and NO_x emissions that would have been generated with biomass incineration for disposal or energy production.

- CH₄ emissions remained minimal or negative due to the nature of the fertilizers and lack of anoxia conditions, confirming the soil's role as a methane sink with this type of field management.
- N₂O emissions were reduced in treatments using organic fertilizers, demonstrating the benefits of slow-release nitrogen sources in mitigating gaseous losses. High emissions were also avoided since the furrows were not flooded using drip irrigation. To adopt this practice, farmers need financial and logistical support to install drip irrigation systems to avoid excessive N₂O emissions, nutrient leakage and waste of water.
- NH₃ volatilization was generally low across treatments, with only mineral-fertilized plots showing notable emissions during the second spinach cycle. Compost and organic-based fertilization strategies did not lead to significant NH₃ losses, reinforcing their suitability for reducing nitrogen volatilization risks.

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Appendix 1

Table S1. Nutrient content of fertilizers expressed in percentages.

	C	N	P	K	Mg
Mineral fertilizer	-	20	7	10	-
Struvite	-	5.7	12.5	-	9.9
Organic nitrogen (Labinor10)	40	10	-	-	-

Table S2. Main characteristics of irrigation water used during the experiment.

pH	7.6	
EC	3.02	dS/m
NO ₃	0.0359	mEq/L
Cl	15.5	mEq/L
SO ₄	5.31	mEq/L
F	0.015	mEq/L
CaCO ₃	259.4	mg/L
CO ₃	<0.06	mEq/L
HCO ₃	9.67	mEq/L
B dissolved	0.41	mg/L
Ca dissolved	9.73	mEq/L
Cu dissolved	<0.05	mg/L
P dissolved	<0.05	mg/L
Fe dissolved	<0.1	mg/L
Mg dissolved	6.84	mEq/L
Mn dissolved	0.039	mg/L
K dissolved	0.888	mEq/L
Na dissolved	14.6	mEq/L
Zn dissolved	<0.05	mg/L

Table S3. Main characteristics of compost.

Amount	322.44	kg/m ³
Dry matter	70.2	%
pH	8.8	
Electric conductivity at 25 C	7.77	d S/m
Organic matter (550 C)	54.7	% s.m.s
C/N relation	14.21	
C	38.6	%
Humic acid	12.6	% s.m.s
Total humic extract	24.2	% s.m.s
Fulvic acid	12.9	% s.m.s
N	2.7122	%
Na	4.55	mg/g
P	4.55	mg/g
K	23.85	mg/g
S	3.38	mg/g
Ca	39.29	mg/g
Mg	5.42	mg/g
Mn	0.14	mg/g
Si	0.28	mg/g
Fe	3.73	mg/g
B	48.39	ug/g
Cd	0.23	ug/g
Cu	42.95	ug/g
Cr	7.54	ug/g
Mo	1.09	ug/g
Cr VI	<0.5	mg/Kg s.m.s
Hg	<0.4	mg/Kg s.m.s
Ni	5.3	ug/g
Pb	11.39	ug/g
Zn	114.99	ug/g
Co	1.74	ug/g
Apparent density	449	kg/m ³

Table S4. Main characteristics of pruning residues used for the spinach and sweet potato cycle.

	Spinach	Sweet potato	Unit
Amount	150	150	ton/ha
N	2210.1	1164.9	kg/ha
C	72417.0	71053.5	kg/ha
P	159.1	165.1	kg/ha
K	992.3	668.1	kg/ha
S	139.4	151.5	kg/ha
Mg	184.8	192.4	kg/ha
Mn	1.5	3.0	kg/ha
Si	27.3	30.3	kg/ha
Fe	21.2	40.9	kg/ha
Ca	1702.9	1908.9	kg/ha
Na	51.5	28.8	kg/ha
B	2.61	1.79	kg/ha
Pb	0.07	0.22	kg/ha
Mo	0.13	0.06	kg/ha
Ni	0.20	0.52	kg/ha
Cr	0.37	0.90	kg/ha
Cu	1.08	1.49	kg/ha
Co	0.003	0.021	kg/ha
Cd	0.003	0.006	kg/ha
Zn	4.00	3.81	kg/ha

TEXTURE

Parameter	Result
• Texture class	Loamy
• Clay	24,0 %
• Lime	28,0 %
• Sand	48,0 %

Risk of compaction

FERTILITY

Parameter	Result	Units	Muy Bajo	Bajo	Normal	Alto	Muy Alto
Electrical cond. (Ext. 1/5)	769	µS/cm a 20 °C		200		400	
pH (Extracted 1/2,5)	7,75	Unidades de pH		6,50		7,50	
Organic matter	1,8400	%		1,2000		2,0000	
Total Nitrogen	1,282	mg/kg		1,000		1,500	
Phosphorous (Olsen)	52,1	mg/kg		20,0		40,0	
Carbonates	5,95	% CaCO3		1,50		4,00	
Calcium availability	14,9	meq/100 g		8,00		14,0	
Magnesium availability	2,40	meq/100 g		1,50		2,50	
Potassium availability	1,14	meq/100 g		0,50		0,80	
Sodium availability	1,68	meq/100 g		0,25		0,75	

MICRONUTRIENTS

Parameter	Result	Units	Muy Bajo	Bajo	Normal	Alto	Muy Alto
Iron (DTPA)	18,0	mg/kg		4,00		10,0	
Manganese (DTPA)	5,11	mg/kg		1,00		5,00	
Copper (DTPA)	32,2	mg/kg		0,40		1,00	
Zinc (DTPA)	18,5	mg/kg		1,00		2,00	

RATIO C/N

Parameter	Result	Units	Muy Bajo	Bajo	Normal	Alto	Muy Alto
C/N ratio	8,32			10,0		15,0	

CATIONS RELATIONSHIP

% of available cations

● Ca Disp.(65%/74%) ● Mg D(25%/12%) ● K D(10%/6%) ● Na D(0%/8%)

Figure S1. Soil test results of the NUTRISOIL experimental field.

Appendix 2

Table S5. Calendar for gas measurements and other activities carried out during the experiments.

Crop cycle	Day	Activities	CO ₂	CH ₄	NH ₃	N ₂ O
Spinach	16/02/2024	Pruning residues incorporation				
	19/02/2024		•	•	•	•
	23/02/2024		•	•	•	
	25/02/2024	Fertilizers application and chamber bases set-up				
	26/02/2024		•	•	•	•
	29/02/2024	Planting and first irrigation				
	04/03/2024		•	•	•	•
	06/03/2024		•	•	•	
	08/03/2024		•	•	•	
	11/03/2024		•	•	•	•
	13/03/2024		•	•	•	
	15/03/2024		•	•	•	
	18/03/2024		•	•	•	•
	20/03/2024		•	•	•	
	25/03/2024		•	•	•	
	28/03/2024		•	•	•	
	02/04/2024		•	•	•	
	05/04/2024		•	•	•	•
	08/04/2024	Harvesting of NPK, SON and COM plots	•	•	•	
	11/04/2024		•	•	•	
	15/04/2024		•	•	•	•
	18/04/2024		•	•	•	
	23/04/2024		•	•	•	•
	25/04/2024	Harvesting of RCWON plots				
	Sweet potato	12/05/2024	Pruning residues incorporation and chamber bases set-up			
13/05/2024			•	•	•	•
22/05/2024		Fertilizers application				
23/05/2024			•	•	•	•
26/05/2024		Planting and first irrigation				
27/05/2024			•	•	•	•
30/05/2024			•	•	•	
03/06/2024			•	•	•	
06/06/2024			•	•	•	
10/06/2024			•	•	•	•
13/06/2024			•	•	•	
17/06/2024			•	•	•	
20/06/2024			•	•	•	
27/06/2024			•	•	•	•
02/07/2024			•	•	•	
10/07/2024			•	•	•	•
16/07/2024			•	•	•	
30/07/2024			•	•	•	•
06/08/2024			•	•	•	
13/08/2024			•	•	•	•

Spinach	20/08/2024		•	•	•		
	27/08/2024		•	•	•	•	
	06/09/2024		•	•	•		
	12/09/2024		•	•	•		
	27/09/2024	Harvesting					
	<hr/>						
	12/10/2024	Pruning residues incorporation and chamber bases set-up					
	15/10/2024		•	•	•	•	
	24/10/2024	Planting and first irrigation					
	29/10/2024		•	•	•	•	
	07/11/2024		•	•	•	•	
	12/11/2024		•	•	•	•	
	19/11/2024		•	•	•	•	
	26/11/2024		•	•	•	•	
	03/12/2024		•	•	•	•	
	13/12/2024		•	•	•	•	
	17/12/2024		•	•	•	•	
	08/01/2025		•	•	•	•	
	14/01/2025	Harvesting		•	•	•	

Table S6. Table with daily emissions of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and NH₃ between the three crop cycles.

		CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O	NH ₃
		Cumulative emissions	Cumulative emissions	Cumulative emissions	Cumulative emissions
Spinach (first cycle)	Days	(ton ha⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹)	(kg ha⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹)
NPK	49	4.1	-74.6	0.36	6.4
SON	49	4.5	-57.1	0.39	7.0
COM	49	3.9	-87.4	0.04	7.5
RCWON	66	24.5	-76.6	0.07	8.9
Spinach (second cycle)	Days	(ton ha⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹)	(kg ha⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹)
NPK	92	9.5	-105.8	0.44	617.4
SON	92	9.9	-88.8	0.30	-309.8
COM	92	7.3	-60.6	0.34	-42.8
RCWON	92	13.4	-69.3	0.21	-59.4
Sweet potato	Days	(ton ha⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹)	(kg ha⁻¹)	(g ha⁻¹)
SON	122	23.7	243.7	0.92	885.7
COM	122	25.8	-621.2	0.08	1371.5
RCWON	122	86.4	81.4	0.12	157.9
RCW	122	82.0	-4307.9	0.04	1136.5